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SURROGATE ADVERTISING OR BRAND EXTENSION ADVERTISING: A NEED FOR STRICT NORMS

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Abstract

Advertising is one the most familiar concept. Without making an effort for advertising, a product cannot be marketed in today's competitive environment. In order to make a product available within reach of people and in their knowledge advertising is essential, now what's comes next is ethical advertising, means advertising must not be in any ways a social waste. Perhaps no company shall indulge in misleading advertising. The purpose of this paper is to highlight the concept of surrogate advertising which is being used by firms of narcotics, drugs, liquor, tobacco, which is being banned from normal advertising. The paper is about reviewing literature, recent surrogate advertisement, citing legal cases against surrogate advertisements in India .Surrogate advertising can be an issue which needs to be understood with respect to India's legal and ethical environments of Promotions. The Information & Broadcasting Ministry of Government of India brought surrogates advertising under the scanner. Some are even airing new ones. It is concern that even young kids have been influenced by surrogate advertisements. It is important to through light on concept which will create awareness among the masses.

Keywords: *Marketing, Advertising, Surrogate Advertising, Banned*

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INTRODUCTION

Advertising is to advocate and further boost the sales of a commodity or service with an aim to grasp the attention of multitude of consumers at one time in order to apprise them about the product peculiarities. Advertising is said to be an efficient and impressive way of conveying the worth of a service or product with heavy exposure to the target customer. It makes use of different kinds of bids to attract and connect with the customers scattered across the globe. After application of Cable Television Networks Regulation Act - 1999, new advertising plea used by most alcohol producing firms to thwart the ban was by what is termed as Surrogate Advertising (Belch & Belch, Purani, 2010). This term means firms begun advertising surrogate goods like audio cassettes, mineral water bottles, soda cans, preserved juices, playing cards, and other such products, under the same brand name for their liquor advertisement used by them earlier before the implementation of the Act. In India many firms can be seen doing the same thing, from Bacardi Blast musical CD's, to Bagpiper Club Soda and Officers Choice playing cards. The veiling good i.e. like the music CD's, mineral water or playing cards are products that might not be advertised if not for this case, it's just a strategic cover up used to achieve top of the recall to mind. While this strategy of advertising continued aiding them to market their alcohol through this medium as many firms didn't even modified their existing advertisements, instead just reinstated them with the text and the voice-overs. One challenge that surrogate advertisement face is as for ethical business practices that a marketer should not misguide customer's especially younger generation or Gen X as they are called towards drinking alcohol.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

In a country like India, products like smoking substances like tobacco, liquor etc. are not culturally acceptable. The Indian Government has banned marketing such products through advertising media. Although a massive country having population of more than a Billion, the actual consumption rate of cigarettes and liquor is large plus it gets huge amounts of rupees revenues to the participants involved in cigarettes, tobacco and liquor markets. Without proper promotional technique a product can never succeed in today's competitive market. But in The Indian subcontinent, a different situation exists, these types of products are significantly popular although generally prohibited to be advertised, which obviously calls for corporate houses to get out of their bounds and find the means to promote their products through mass media even

though such kind of process may be legally objectionable. The key solution to this is Brand Extension Advertising. The brand name remains same but products marketed are altered so as the brand leave its impact on the prospective consumer minds. So the need of the hour is to understand the depth and use of such methods adopted by various marketers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- The study aims at analyzing surrogate advertising practices followed.
- Discussing the role played by Government, corporate and media.
- To provide inputs for the respective media, promotion and broadcasting.
- Finally making note for the corporate houses about advertising ethics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Classical 4Ps of Marketing Mix i.e. Product, Price, Promotion, Place is of endless use to marketing academicians and practitioners for constructing an integrated marketing strategy. Along with market segmentation, target marketing and market positioning, the traditional marketing mix of 4 P's plays a dominant role for conniving marketing guideline or plan originating in early level connected with fresh product development until eventual maintenance of the market share. In spite of exactly what content material inside the product is used, the amount at which it is priced in the market, just how strenuous the marketing is and in addition how large is the coverage of product distribution, a definite identity to distinguish the product from different available merchandise available in the market is crucial. In the field of marketing, such identification designated to a particular product is known as brand. A brand name is generated to be able to create prolonged term-chained connections concerning corporation and consumers. Seeing that more and more substitute products are obtainable in the market today, consumers take bigger faith in the brand they will depend upon, in comparison to goods which are giving values close to their requirements.

A brand can be a singling out logo, few specific words, or some kind of mark that differentiates a particular product or corporate brand from its respective competitor. Generally product or company brands are documented or registered (trademarked) with some regulatory authority so some other party cannot use them freely. For many goods as well as businesses, the process of

branding is surely a crucial part of marketing procedure. A series of programs to advertise goods relying upon on their brand image is known as branding. Branding is crucial requirement to enhance perceived customer value. Successful branding plans helps in creation of loyalty towards the brand and consequently transmits this loyalty to extension of the brand. Identical with individuals, a brand comes with an image as accretion of some peculiar qualities. Physical quality of a product is one of the most perceptible and also least complicated to discover, belongs to this accretion of features. In long run, good quality of a product is anticipated individually from the brand name and its brand image. Many argue that image of the brand is far more crucial than the quality of respective physical product. In execution of brand extension strategy, much talked about and hyped product with a well recognized brand image is perceived to be more success than compared with the one having a low profile brand image.

Brand extension is actually an element of brand management which may be useful in order to expand and also help in elevating the extant brand by stepping into fresh merchandise group by development of a new product. Affirmative portraits and clouts of already existing brand or parent brand are accordingly leveraged to create similar success story for the new brand. Brand extension is progressively used more by companies as an element of strategy for development of a new product. It is perceived as one of the methods to attain bundled architecture of brand. It may include making use of the same brand on already existing good of parent brand for marketing of new product in a separate category i.e. extension of the brand which might increases the rate of acceptance of new product and helps in development of affirmative intention in the customer to purchase the product. The strategy cultivates productivity on advertising and expenditures on promotions yet still be able to create an all new market segment. The extended brand company may not be in position to allocate funds for marketing at the same level as allocated by their parent brand, yet may create similar success story. A robust or secure prominence of parent brand helps in minimizing risk for the new product by reaping benefits on customers' familiarity and involvement with the established brand.

In case of Surrogate Advertising, through the use of the brand image of one product which has legal permission to be promoted, the marketer seeks to market a different product which may be legally not allowed to be advertised. Over here, the product having legal permission for promotion is called surrogate product (example is Royal Challengers IPL team), the product

banned from promotion is actual product (example Royal Challenges liquor). In other words Surrogate Advertising means duplication of brand image of one product used extensively for the promotion of the other product. It means advertising another product while using identical brand as the first product is not permitted to be advertised in the market according to the laws of the land. In Surrogate Advertising, a product, called as "Surrogate Product" which is different from main product is advertised under the same brand name such advertising is called as "Surrogate Advertising". Examples of such products may include CDs, Clothing, Mineral water, Soda bottles, Fashion Accessories, Sponsoring of popular events, Sports accessories etc. Such practices is generally called as brand extension strategy by the firms while critics call it as surrogate advertising which at times can be termed as unethical.

SURROGATE MARKETING

Dr Anbumani Ramadoss, Former Union Minister, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare on 28 April 2008 when questioned by media about his views on alleged promotion of surrogate marketing by Indian Premiere league IPL he was quoted, "It is unfortunate that things like these are happening out there and we will be taking up the issue with the Information and Broadcasting ministry. But then yesterday the Supreme Court has not taken any cognizance as well" He condemned IPL when team owned by Dr. Vijay Mallya, the Chairman and Head of UB group, after buying out the Bangalore team named it as Royal Challengers Bangalore promoting the liquor brand namely "Royal Challenge" which is one of the merchandise produced by United Beverages Group. The Minister raised his doubts and showed his displeasure that UB Group was adopting Surrogate Marketing practice wherein banned to advertise and promote product i.e. Royal Challenge liquor will be promoted and in constant eyes of media as well as consumers through the Cricket Team of Royal Challengers Bangalore. Advertising for Liquor and Cigarette firms has been banned by the Indian Government from the year 1995 under the Cable Television Network (Regulation) Act 1995. Even law prohibits any kind of direct or indirect advertisement and promotion of these items in the public realm as mentioned in Rule 7 of the Cable Television Rules, 1999.

The main desire behind ban of such kinds of products was discouraging the people from consumption of harmful products like tobacco and alcohol. Liquor industry in India is said to be huge, which attracts many other players. Larger the market is, bigger is the size of promotion it

requires. Along with Domestic competition, firms face clash from International players too. Alcohol and Cigarette are the highest revenue creators through the means of taxes and duties collected on these items by the Government. Apparent approval of the advertising in such sectors is unacceptable. While on other hand, it cannot be allowed by the Government for the public promotion of liquor. But amusingly, this led to biggest satire of the decade for the country as though sales are not restricted for these goods but their promotion is contraband. Marketers have found a lot of loopholes in the process and used new and innovative ways for promotion of these banned goods, Surrogate Marketing technique is one of such innovation.

The Corporate houses are advertising the brand with the same brand name and different product. Branding is promotion of the products which creates the sense of differentiation from other products in the same market. Here, brand may be symbol, name, image, logo etc. Difference in surrogate marketing is that the promoted brand is used to remember some other product. Various means of advertising are selected for promoting the product. The firms perform more the function of building process of the brand rather than selling the original product. This kind of deceitful demeanor of firms is trying the levels of tolerance of governing bodies. Therefore the unethical Surrogate Advertising is readopted as Brand Extension Advertising.

BRAND EXTENSION ADVERTISING PRACTICES

In two situations surrogate marketing can be used. The first when the firm "Subcontracts" the whole marketing function and the troop which provides service is "Surrogate Marketing Department". Second one is duplicating image of brand of one product largely for the promotion of another product by same brand by the use of Broadcasting Media, Print, Internet, and outdoor promotions. Providing Sponsorships for Sports, Fashion, Leisure and other cultural events using brand name of the liquor brand falls under this category.

Some practices that can be observed in actual business practices are:

- (1) Haywards 5000 alcohol under Darting Kits.
- (2) Bagpiper Whiskey with Bagpiper Club Soda.
- (3) Kingfisher Beer with Mineral Water.
- (4) Royal Stag Wine with Royal Stag Music CDs.
- (5) Royal Challenge Whiskey with Golf Accessories.

- (6) Charms Cigarette under blanket of Audiocassettes and CDs.
- (7) Smirnoff Vodka with Fruit Juices.
- (8) Royal Challenge with IPL Cricket Team Royal Challengers Bangalore.
- (9) McDowell alcohol with No.1 Soda
- (10) Wills cigarette with Sports Gear.

Below chart show practices by corporate in terms of surrogacy

LEGITIMATE BUSINESS	SURROGATE ADVERTISEMENT
Mc Dowell’s Walt whisky	Mc Dowell’s soda/water
Radico khaitan’s 8 pm whisky	Radico khaitan’s water
Hayward’s 500 beer	Hayward’s soda/water
Derby special	Derby special soda
Bacardi liquor	Bacardi blast cds and cassettes
Bagpiper liquor	Bagpiper soda and cassettes
Four square cigarettes	Four square white water rafting
Kingfisher beer	Kingfisher bottled drinking water
Smirnoff vodka	Smirnoff cds and cassettes
Red and white cigarettes	Red and white bravery awards
Pan Parag gutka	Pan Parag pan masala
Rajnigandha tobacco mix	Rajnigandha pan masala
Chaini Khaini	Chaini Chaini pan masala
Gopal Zarda	Gopal Supari 132
Pataka 502 Bidi	Pataka 502 Tea

LEGAL REGULATION ON SURROGATE ADVERTISING IN INDIA

The **ASCI Code** provides that advertisements of products whose advertising is prohibited or restricted by law or by the **ASCI Code** must not circumvent such restrictions by purporting advertisements for other products the advertising of which is not prohibited or restricted by law or by **ASCI Code**. To determine if there is an indirect advertisement of prohibited products due attention shall be given to the following:

- a. Visual content of the advertisement must depict only the product being advertised and not the prohibited or restricted product in any form or manner.
- b. The advertisement must not make any direct or indirect reference to the prohibited or restricted products.
- c. The advertisement must not create any nuances or phrases promoting prohibited products.
- d. The advertisement must not use particular colors and layout or presentations associated with prohibited or restricted products.
- e. The advertisement must not use situations typical for promotion of prohibited or restricted products when advertising the other products.

The Cable Television Networks Rules, 1994 has imposed quite similar regulations to curb surrogate advertising.

NEED OF THE HOUR

1. Developing an explicit plan of action.
2. Code to differentiate between acceptable advertising from unacceptable advertising.
3. Translucent laws for banning such kind surrogate promotion.
4. More powers in hands of ASCI.
5. Increase consumer awareness.
6. Strict actions against those involved to set lesson for future wrong doers.

ADVERTISING ETHICS AND PRINCIPLES

Ethics provides a general idea about what is considered right or what is considered wrong. They are concerned with attitudes and values. Ethics are epitomized in conventions or rules of management. American Advertising Federation has defined Advertising Ethics as follows:

- (1) Truth: Advertisement of the product or service shall tell the truth only, and should reveal all the relevant facts, any omission of facts which would may mislead the public is unacceptable. - Substantiation: Advertising claims should be validated by evidence claim in hold of the said advertiser and respective advertising agency, before making such claims.

- (2) Comparisons: Advertisement shall abstain from making false claims, misleading facts, or making unsubstantiated statements or any kind claims about competitor's goods.
 - (3) Bait Advertising: Company advertising shall refrain itself from offering goods or service at offer prices unless and until it is a bona fide attempt to genuinely sell the product or service rather than just a instrument to lure consumers other generally high priced goods or service.
 - (4) Guarantees and Warranties: Guarantees and warranties should be advertised explicitly, with ample knowledge to inform customers of about their principle terms and conditions or, when time and space regulations avert such confessions, the advertisement should precisely convey where full text of warranty and guarantee should be studied before making the purchase.
 - (5) Price Claims: Advertisements shall be avoiding any kind of false, misleading and price saving claims which are not offering actual provable savings.
 - (6) Testimonials: Advertising which consist of endorsements shall be narrowed down witnesses reflect actual and truthful opinion or experience.
 - (7) Taste & Decency: Advertising should be free of any kind of illustrations or implications or false claims or statements which may be abhorrent to good taste and against public decency.
- Adopted by the American Advertising Federation Board of Directors, March 2, 1984, San Antonio, Texas.

CONCLUSION

Surrogate Advertising is a concern which requires understanding and analyzing it in respect with Indian's legal environment and ethical background. The liquor industry and narcotics being restricted from normal promotion of its basic crux of the message to the congregation or audience has left unattended thereby a probable choice of path which Companies are left to follow practices such as Surrogate Advertising, due to its efficacy in terms of creating awareness recall in the minds of consumers and leading to sales of particular product or service. But marketing channels like mobile marketing or direct marketing are the legal options which they can follow without raising any ethical issues. The Information & Broadcasting Ministry of Government of India plans to bring more Surrogates Advertising practitioners under the scanner. The legitimate Brand Extension may be dismayed due to curbs on surrogate advertising, that

being said producers or firms going for bona fide brand extension should adhere to condition of satisfactory availability of surrogate advertisement product. Further this is an area of awareness so government must make all efforts to educate people at large about this kind of advertising and corporate must also indulge in helping the youth and contribute towards society rather than increasing their own sales and profits.

BIBLOGRAPHY

- [1].Stuart, Ewen. Captains of Consciousness: Advertising and the Social Roots of the Consumer Culture, Basic Books, ISBN13: 9780465021550, ISBN10: 0465021557.
- [2].Williamson, Judith (1994): Decoding Advertisements (Ideas in Progress), Marion Boyars Publishers Ltd (March 1, 1994),ISBN-10: 0714526150, ISBN-13: 978-0714526157.
- [3].Graydon, Shari (2003) "Made You Look - How Advertising Works and Why You Should Know", Toronto: Annick Press, ISBN 1-55037-814-7.
- [4]. Johnson, J. Douglas, "Advertising Today", Chicago: Science Research Associates, 1978. ISBN 0-574-19355-38
- [5]. Klein, Naomi (2000) No Logo . Harper-Collins, ISBN 0-00-653040-0.

WEB REFERENCES

- [1]. <http://www.dancewithshadows.com>
- [2]. <http://www.icmrindia.org/casestudies/catalogue/Marketing/MKTG024.html>
- [3]. <http://readbetweentheps.blogspot.com/2006/02/surrogate-advertising-enforced.html>
- [4]. <http://www.managementparadise.com>
- [5]. <http://www.livemint.com/2008/04/29171420/Ramadoss-targets-IPL-on-surrog.html>
- [6]. <http://www.indiantelevision.com/mam/headlines/y2k8/mar/marmam71.php>
- [7].<http://www.aaf.org/default.asp?id=37>
- [8].<http://www.articlesbase.com/advertising-articles/surrogate-marketing-a-new-extension-in-advertising-5871583.html>